

Design and Simulation of High-Efficiency Two-Dimensional Carbon Nitride (C₂N-h2D) Solar Cell with SnS (HTL) and TiO₂ (ETL) via SCAPS-1D

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Abstract

Due to surge in energy demand, recent discoveries of two-dimensional (2D) materials have sparked an enormous interest in green and affordable energy. This paper is focused on numerically investigation of two-dimensional C₂N-based solar cell with a novel heterostructure (Ni/SnS/C₂N/TiO₂/ITO/Al) using SCAPS-1D simulator. Aim of this study is to examine the impact of SnS hole-transport layer (HTL) and TiO₂ electron-transport layer (ETL) on our proposed device. Based on the device structure, the energy band alignment, thickness, and doping density of C₂N, SnS, TiO₂, C₂N defect density, back-contact electrode (BCE) work function, and operating temperature are examined to improve the cell performance. According to simulations, the suitable thickness and doping concentration for the C₂N are obtained at 1000 nm and 10¹⁵ cm⁻³, respectively. It is found that increasing the acceptor doping density of SnS contributes more to device efficiency than increasing its thickness. Further, the back-contact electrode (BCE) work function above 5.0 eV significantly enhanced the cell efficiency. The optimized results reveal that the solar cell performance significantly improved with the presented cell configuration, reaching to highest PCE of 23.41%. This work would have a positive impact on the production of emerging solar cells.

Keywords: Two-dimensional material, C₂N, SnS, TiO₂, SCAPS-1D.

Introduction

Currently, the global energy demand is dependent on fossil fuels, which are limited and have negative implications on our environment. Transitioning from conventional to renewable energy sources will play a vital role in meeting our energy needs sustainably. Among alternative sources, solar energy is an abundant and clean energy source that could be easily converted into useful electricity using photovoltaic (PV) technology. In the last decade, rapid growth has been seen in PVs, contributing to almost 3% of the world's electricity generation in 2021 (Masterson, 2021). This progress has been significantly influenced by advancements in production processes and materials. The PV market is currently dominated by highly efficient silicon-based solar cells, which account for more than 80% of installed capacity and contribute to 90% of the market share (Pastuszak & Węgierek, 2022). The efficiency of silicon solar cells has reached around 27% (NREL, 2021). However, the high production cost prevents it from becoming a terawatt (GW) technology. Other solar cells, such as cadmium telluride (CdTe), copper indium gallium selenide (CIGS), gallium arsenide (GaAs), quantum-dot, and perovskite, also exhibit high efficiencies. However, large-scale production of these materials is limited due to their expensive manufacturing processes, rare (indium and tellurium), toxic (cadmium), and unstable (perovskite and quantum dot) elements (Roy,

Ghosh, Barclay, Khare, & Cuce, 2022). Therefore, it is essential to prepare new materials that could be used as an alternative to today's solar power technology.

Graphene, a two-dimensional (2D) material, has shown remarkable electronic and magnetic properties over the past few years (B. Zhou, Wang, Dong, Zhang, & Mi, 2017). The huge potential of graphene grabs the attention of the worldwide research community to synthesize other 2D materials for energy conversion applications. In 2015, a research group at the Ulsan National Institute of Science & Technology, South Korea, synthesized a novel two-dimensional carbon nitride (C_2N -h2D) using a simple wet chemical reaction (Mahmood et al., 2015). C_2N has a unique pore structure of tightly bonded nitrogen to carbon atoms, making it an ideal material for application in medicine, energy storage, and gas adsorption (Tian, López-Salas, Liu, Liu, & Antonietti, 2020). According to reports, C_2N can be used as a high-performance absorber layer in solar cells owing to its suitable direct band gap, high thermal and chemical stability, environmentally-friendly nature, and high absorption coefficient (Bafekry, Stampfl, Ghergherehchi, & Shayesteh, 2020; Sun, Zhang, Li, & Yang, 2016). Nevertheless, very little study has been reported on C_2N as a PV material. Therefore, it is crucial to study the properties of C_2N as a layer in solar cells for future developments. (X. Zhou & Han, 2020) coupled CdS as a window layer material with an HTL-free C_2N -based device and attained a PCE of above 17%. Recently, (Yasin, Waar, Al Zoubi, & Moustafa, 2021) have numerically investigated IGZO buffer layer in C_2N -based solar cell, which improved the cell efficiency to 18.57%. Up to now, C_2N has been only structured with ETLs as the charge transporting material. In this study, our purpose is to examine the influence of the TiO_2 (ETL) and SnS (HTL) on the performance of C_2N -based solar cells.

Figure 1: Schematic architecture of C_2N -based solar cell

Computational Methodology and Simulation Parameters

The numerical study of the proposed device structure (Ni/SnS/ C_2N / TiO_2 /ITO/Al), as illustrated in Figure 1, was implemented in solar cell Capacitance Simulator (SCAPS-1D). The SCAPS-1D programme is developed by Dr. Marc Burgelman and his colleague at the Department of Electronics and Information

Systems (ELIS) of the University of Gent, Belgium (Burgelman, Nollet, & Degrave, 2000). This programme mainly solves three basic semiconductor equations (Moustafa & Alzoubi, 2018):

$$\text{Poisson equation: } \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\epsilon_o \epsilon_r \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial x} \right) = -q \left(p - n + N_D^+ - N_A^- + \frac{\rho}{q} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Continuity equation for electrons: } - \left(\frac{1}{q} \right) \frac{\partial J_n}{\partial x} - u_n + G = \frac{\partial n}{\partial t} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Continuity equation for holes: } - \left(\frac{1}{q} \right) \frac{\partial J_p}{\partial x} - u_p + G = \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} \quad (3)$$

Where Ψ represents the electrostatic potential wave function, ϵ_o and ϵ_r symbolize for permittivity of free space and dielectric permittivity, respectively, ρ represents defect charge density, G is the rate of charge carrier generation, N_D^+ and N_A^- denoted for ionized donor and acceptor densities, and J_n and J_p represent the current densities for electron and hole. Initially, the material parameters for each layer have been carefully selected from authentic literature, as summarized in Table 1. Then we optimized the C₂N thickness and acceptor doping concentration in the range of 300 nm - 2000 nm and 10^{13} cm^{-3} - 10^{19} cm^{-3} , respectively, while keeping the thickness of HTL and ETL constant at 50 nm. Further, the absorber layer is studied under low, average, and high defect levels. After optimizing the absorber layer, the same procedure was adopted for the HTL and ETL. Finally, the solar cell performance was examined at different back-contact electrode work function and operating temperature.

Table 1: Initial input parameters for C₂N-based solar cell (Rahman, 2021; Yasin et al., 2021; X. Zhou & Han, 2020)

Parameters	ITO	TiO ₂ (ETL)	C ₂ N (absorber)	SnS (HTL)
Thickness (nm)	50	20-60	300	100-500
Bandgap, E _g (eV)	3.5	3.26	1.8	1.6
Electron affinity, χ (eV)	4.6	4.20	4.42	4.1
Dielectric permittivity, ϵ_r	8.9	10	4.5	13
Effective CB density of states, N_c (cm ⁻³)	2.2×10^{18}	2.0×10^{17}	1.0×10^{19}	1.18×10^{18}
Effective VB density of states, N_v (cm ⁻³)	1.8×10^{19}	6.0×10^{17}	1.0×10^{19}	4.46×10^{18}
Electron thermal velocity (cms ⁻¹)	1×10^7	1×10^7	1×10^7	1×10^7
Hole thermal velocity (cms ⁻¹)	1×10^7	1×10^7	1×10^7	1×10^7
Electron mobility, μ_n (cm ² V ⁻¹ S ⁻¹)	10	100	13	15
Hole mobility, μ_p (cm ² V ⁻¹ S ⁻¹)	10	25	20.6	100
Donor concentration, N_D (cm ⁻³)	1×10^{21}	10^{16} - 10^{20}	0	0
Acceptor concentration, N_A (cm ⁻³)	0	0	1.0×10^{15}	10^{16} - 10^{19}
Capture cross-section of electrons (cm ⁻²)	1×10^{17}	1.0×10^{-16}	1.0×10^{-14}	1×10^{17}
Capture cross-section of holes (cm ⁻²)	1×10^{-15}	1.0×10^{-16}	1.0×10^{-17}	1×10^{-15}
Defect density, N_t (cm ⁻³)	1×10^{-16}	10^{16}	1.0×10^{15}	1.0×10^{-16}
Defect type	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral
Defect distribution	Single	Single	Gaussian	Single

Results and Discussion

In solar cells, the back-contact electrode (BCE) enables the efficient collection of photogenerated charge carriers and significantly influences overall device performance. In our simulations, the work function of BCE is changed from 4.9 eV to 5.4 eV and the normalized PV parameters are depicted in Figure 2. According to simulated results, the device performance parameters greatly improved by increasing the work function above 5 eV. We employed Nickel (Ni) as the BCE with the work function of 5.35 eV (Baker, Johnson, & Maire, 1971; Herbert, 1977), as Ni forms very low resistance ohmic contact with SnS (Hajzus et al., 2018).

Figure 2: Impact of varying back-contact metal work function on normalized performance parameters of C_2N -based solar cell

The energy band alignment of the C_2N -based heterostructure (Ni/SnS/ C_2N /TiO₂/ITO/Al) is presented in Figure 3. At the C_2N /TiO₂ interface, a small spike (CBO of +0.22) energy forms, which helps in the smooth flow of photogenerated electrons through the ETL into the front electrode. On the other hand, at the SnS/ C_2N interface, a large spike (CBO of +0.32) energy generates, which blocks the photogenerated electrons at the junction from reaching the back electrode. Moreover, SnS has a slightly higher valance band minimum (VBM) than the absorber layer, which makes the holes easily collected at the back electrode while blocking them at the TiO₂ layer.

Figure 3: Energy band alignment diagram of C_2N -based heterostructure solar cell

In solar cells, maximum absorption of the incident light takes place in the absorber layer, hence significantly influencing their performance. In this study, the thickness of C_2N (absorber layer) is changed from 300 nm to 2000 nm. The PV parameters: V_{oc} , J_{sc} , FF , and PCE improve with increasing the C_2N thickness, as shown in Figure 4 (a-d). The FF starts to decline after 1000 nm, as can be seen from Figure 4 (c). The FF variation is attributed to the decrease in charge carriers' diffusion length relative to the absorber layer thickness. Thereby, the recombination of charge carriers becomes active, changing series resistance and power depletion, resulting in a drop of FF . Above 1000 nm, the charge carriers partially recombine in the absorber layer, leading to saturation in efficiency. Therefore, the suitable thickness of the C_2N layer is considered at 1000 nm with obtained PCE of 18.01%.

Figure 4: (a-d) Behaviour in PV parameters with C_2N layer thickness

According to reported studies, C_2N may contain some deep defect points, such as impurities, crystallographic defects, and vacancies (Tromer, da Luz, Ferreira, & Pereira, 2017; Zhang, Zhang, Yang, & Zhou, 2018). Generally, these deep defect points act as recombination centers for photogenerated charge carriers. As shown in Figure 5 (a), the efficiency sharply decreased when the C_2N defect density increased above 10^{14} cm^{-3} . Additionally, high defect density can tune the bandgap of the C_2N layer, contributing inversely to the light absorption process, as illustrated in Figure 5 (b). Experimentally, it is challenging to maintain extremely low defect density in C_2N . Therefore, we performed our simulations at 10^{14} cm^{-3} to achieve optimum results.

Figure 5: Impact of varying defect density of C₂N layer on (a) Efficiency and (b) Quantum efficiency

Furthermore, variations in PV parameters were observed with increasing the C₂N acceptor doping concentration in the range 10¹³ cm⁻³-10¹⁹ cm⁻³, as shown in Figure 6 (a-d). From 10¹⁶ cm⁻³-10¹⁹ cm⁻³, the V_{oc} increased significantly due to decrease in reverse saturation current. Initially, the device achieved highest J_{sc} at the doping rate of 10¹³ cm⁻³, but it dropped considerably at high doping concentration, which is ascribed to the short lifetime of charge carriers at the interface. The sharp decline in FF above 10¹⁷ cm⁻³ is due to an increase in series resistance of the cell. According to the obtained results, the device produced highest PCE of 18.01% at 10¹⁵ cm⁻³.

Figure 6: (a-d) Influence of C₂N doping concentration on PV parameters

For efficient charge carrier separation, SnS (HTL) was employed to transport the generated holes in the C₂N layer to the positive electrode. In this study, the SnS thickness and acceptor doping concentration are optimized in the range of 100 nm - 600 nm and 10¹⁶ cm⁻³-10¹⁹ cm⁻³, respectively. From Figure 7 (a) and (b), it can be seen that when the doping concentration of SnS is increased, the efficiency increased significantly than that of the increase in thickness. The optimum thickness and doping density for the SnS layer are adopted at 300 nm and 10¹⁹ cm⁻³ with an efficiency of 23.39%.

Figure 7: Variation in solar cell efficiency at increasing SnS (a) Thickness and (b) Doping density

In the proposed n-i-p device structure, the incident light penetrates through TiO₂ (ETL) into the absorber layer. Therefore, thickness and doping optimization of the ETL layer is crucial to improve solar cell performance. The thickness and donor concentration of the TiO₂ layer varied in the range of 10 nm - 100 nm and 10¹⁶ cm⁻³ - 10²⁰ cm⁻³, respectively. As illustrated in Figure 8 (a), when the TiO₂ thickness increased, efficiency dropped sharply due to low light transmittance and high absorption in the ETL, resulting in low electron-hole pairs generation. However, decreasing thickness below a certain point could be inclined to mainly two types of problems; (i) the device performance could be reversed by switching it to the Schottky barrier structure and (ii) fabrication limitation. Therefore, the suitable thickness of the TiO₂ layer is selected at 50 nm. On the other hand, the solar cell efficiency increased with increasing TiO₂ layer doping density but gradually declined after reaching a maximum point of 10¹⁷ cm⁻³, as shown in Figure 8 (b). After optimization of TiO₂ thickness and doping concentration, the maximum performance for the C₂N-based solar cell is recorded at a PCE of 23.41 %.

Figure 8: Solar cell efficiency at varying TiO₂ (a) Thickness and (b) Acceptor density

The operating temperature of solar cells determines their stability. High operating temperatures deteriorate the cell layers and device performance. We investigated the stability of our optimized device by changing its temperature from 300 K to 500 K. As shown in Figure 9, the solar cell efficiency sharply dropped from 23.41% to 15.77% at 300 K and 500 K, respectively. The deep decline in efficiency is attributed to the distortion of the cell's layers, which shortened the diffusion length of the photogenerated charge carriers. Consequently, high recombination rate carried by an increase in series resistance prevents the collection of photogenerated charge carriers at the back electrode.

Figure 9: Impact of operating temperatures on C₂N-based solar cell efficiency

Conclusions

With promising PV properties, C₂N-h2D could be a new addition to energy conversion materials. In this study, we simulated a C₂N-based heterojunction device using SCAPS-1D software. The simulated results showed that by introducing SnS-HTL, the solar cell efficiency improved compared to previously reported HTL-free C₂N-based solar cells. This study also demonstrated TiO₂-ETL to be essential for efficient energy band alignment. The impact of back-contact electrode was also examined, and it was found that the work function above 5 eV significantly increased the device efficiency. Based on the optimized data, the optimum performance for C₂N, SnS, and TiO₂ thicknesses was obtained at 1000 nm, 300 nm, and 50 nm with doping densities of 10¹⁵ cm⁻³, 10¹⁹ cm⁻³, and 10¹⁷ cm⁻³, respectively. After optimization, the proposed device achieved an efficiency of 23.41 % at a temperature of 300 K. Further, the device stability was evaluated at different temperatures ranging from 300 K to 500 K, which showed that the solar cell performance could only be affected at extreme temperatures. The results of this contribution highlight the potential of C₂N-based heterojunction solar cells and other 2D materials as the next-generation emerging PV devices.

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